

Higher Order Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Order 1220 Multiples of 4

Inder J. Taneja¹

The work is also available at author's site:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19291>

Abstract

*This work bring for first time in the literature of magic squares a **prime magic square of order 1220×1220**. All the prime numbers are distinct. This **prime magic square is block-structured** with equal sums prime magic squares of order 4. This work is studied in levels or steps. Before bring prime magic square of order 1220, we brought first the prime magic squares of orders 120, 160, 324, 484, 656, 986 and then finally the order 1220. The idea of studying first the lower orders is that we are able to bring lower orders with less magic squares sums. In each case the magic sum of order 4 is different, but are of equal sums in each level. It goes on increasing as the order of magic squares increases.*

*The **excel files** of complete work are also attached*

Keywords: magic squares, prime magic squares, block-wise magic squares, concentric magic squares, recreational mathematics.

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012).
Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).
E-mail: ijthaneja@gmail.com;
Web-sites: <http://inderjtaneja.com/>; <http://numbers-magic.com/>;
Twitter: @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

Contents

1 Introduction	3
1.1 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 8	3
1.2 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 9	3
2 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 10	4
2.1 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 11	5
2.2 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 12	5
3 Prime-Structured Magic Squares of Order 1220×1220	7
3.1 Level 1: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 120×120	8
3.2 Level 2: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 160×160	10
3.3 Level 3: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 324×324	12
3.4 Level 4: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 484×484	14
3.5 Level 5: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 656×656	16
3.6 Level 6: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 896×896	18
3.7 Level 7: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 1220×1220	20
4 Author’s Contribution to Recreation of Numbers and Magic Squares	22

1 Introduction

During past years, the author studied block-wise constructions of magic squares. The work for the magic square of orders 8 to 47. Below are few examples:

1.1 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 8

Let's consider a **pandiagonal** of order 8 is given by

8x8	pan	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
260	7	60	1	62	15	52	9	54	260	260
260	2	61	8	59	10	53	16	51	260	260
260	64	3	58	5	56	11	50	13	260	260
260	57	6	63	4	49	14	55	12	260	260
260	23	44	17	46	31	36	25	38	260	260
260	18	45	24	43	26	37	32	35	260	260
260	48	19	42	21	40	27	34	29	260	260
	41	22	47	20	33	30	39	28	260	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

It is composed four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.

1.2 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 9

Let's consider a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 is given by

9x9	pan	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369
369	22	71	30	27	64	32	20	69	34	369
369	35	21	67	28	23	72	33	25	65	369
369	66	31	26	68	36	19	70	29	24	369
369	40	8	75	45	1	77	38	6	79	369
369	80	39	4	73	41	9	78	43	2	369
369	3	76	44	5	81	37	7	74	42	369
369	58	53	12	63	46	14	56	51	16	369
369	17	57	49	10	59	54	15	61	47	369
	48	13	62	50	18	55	52	11	60	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** (sum of only rows and columns) with equal magic sums.

Below is another example where blocks of order 3 are magic squares, but the magic square of order 9 is not **pandiagonal**:

9 mgc										369
	31	36	29	76	81	74	13	18	11	369
	30	32	34	75	77	79	12	14	16	369
	35	28	33	80	73	78	17	10	15	369
	22	27	20	40	45	38	58	63	56	369
	21	23	25	39	41	43	57	59	61	369
	26	19	24	44	37	42	62	55	60	369
	67	72	65	4	9	2	49	54	47	369
	66	68	70	3	5	7	48	50	52	369
	71	64	69	8	1	6	53	46	51	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sums.

2 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 10

Let's consider a magic square of order 10 with inner part as magic square of order 8 with blocks of order 4 is given by

10x10	mgc										505
	91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92	505
	13	47	58	19	78	39	66	27	70	88	505
	89	22	75	50	55	30	67	42	63	12	505
	11	82	23	54	43	74	31	62	35	90	505
	96	51	46	79	26	59	38	71	34	5	505
	1	48	57	20	77	40	65	28	69	100	505
	93	21	76	49	56	29	68	41	64	8	505
	7	81	24	53	44	73	32	61	36	94	505
	95	52	45	80	25	60	37	72	33	6	505
	9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10	505
	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

The blocks of order 8 are equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 10.

2.1 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 11

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 with inner part as magic square of order 9 is given by

11x11	mgc											671
	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671
	121	21	38	43	55	60	68	80	85	99	1	671
	119	53	58	72	75	92	97	28	33	41	3	671
	117	82	87	95	26	31	45	48	65	70	5	671
	115	47	25	30	69	50	64	94	81	89	7	671
	11	67	54	62	101	79	84	42	23	37	111	671
	13	96	77	91	40	27	35	74	52	57	109	671
	15	34	39	29	59	73	51	90	98	76	107	671
	17	63	71	49	88	93	83	32	46	24	105	671
	19	86	100	78	36	44	22	61	66	56	103	671
	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

The blocks of order 8 are equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 10.

2.2 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are three different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 12. First as magic square formed by 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums. Second as magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. Third as 4 blocks of order 6 with equal magic sums. In the first two cases, the magic square of order 12 is **pandiagonal**, while third case, it is just a magic square.

• Blocks of Order 3

12x12	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	98	1	51	72	22	119	78	28	125	140	43	93	870	
870	3	50	97	118	71	24	124	77	30	45	92	139	870	
870	49	99	2	23	120	70	29	126	76	91	141	44	870	
870	131	34	84	87	37	134	57	7	104	113	16	66	870	
870	36	83	130	133	86	39	103	56	9	18	65	112	870	
870	82	132	35	38	135	85	8	105	55	64	114	17	870	
870	67	117	20	5	102	52	47	144	94	73	123	26	870	
870	21	68	115	100	53	6	142	95	48	27	74	121	870	
870	116	19	69	54	4	101	96	46	143	122	25	75	870	
870	88	138	41	32	129	79	14	111	61	58	108	11	870	
870	42	89	136	127	80	33	109	62	15	12	59	106	870	
	137	40	90	81	31	128	63	13	110	107	10	60	870	
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	

• Blocks of Order 4

12x12	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	7	140	1	142	15	132	9	134	23	124	17	126	870	
870	2	141	8	139	10	133	16	131	18	125	24	123	870	
870	144	3	138	5	136	11	130	13	128	19	122	21	870	
870	137	6	143	4	129	14	135	12	121	22	127	20	870	
870	31	116	25	118	39	108	33	110	47	100	41	102	870	
870	26	117	32	115	34	109	40	107	42	101	48	99	870	
870	120	27	114	29	112	35	106	37	104	43	98	45	870	
870	113	30	119	28	105	38	111	36	97	46	103	44	870	
870	55	92	49	94	63	84	57	86	71	76	65	78	870	
870	50	93	56	91	58	85	64	83	66	77	72	75	870	
870	96	51	90	53	88	59	82	61	80	67	74	69	870	
	89	54	95	52	81	62	87	60	73	70	79	68	870	
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	

• Blocks of Order 6

12	mgc												870
	1	143	142	141	2	6	19	125	124	123	20	24	870
	138	8	136	9	11	133	120	26	118	27	29	115	870
	132	131	15	16	128	13	114	113	33	34	110	31	870
	18	14	129	130	17	127	36	32	111	112	35	109	870
	7	134	10	135	137	12	25	116	28	117	119	30	870
	139	5	3	4	140	144	121	23	21	22	122	126	870
	55	89	88	87	56	60	37	107	106	105	38	42	870
	84	62	82	63	65	79	102	44	100	45	47	97	870
	78	77	69	70	74	67	96	95	51	52	92	49	870
	72	68	75	76	71	73	54	50	93	94	53	91	870
	61	80	64	81	83	66	43	98	46	99	101	48	870
	85	59	57	58	86	90	103	41	39	40	104	108	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

More on these kind of magic squares can be seen in author's work [26, 27, 28]. The aim of this work write magic squares with blocks of order 4 with distinct prime number entries. We concentrated blocks of equal sum prime magic squares of order 4. The total work is up to order 1220×1220 . Since the order is too high, the work is given in parts. There are total seven parts to reach up to the proposed order.

Based on the idea of **blocks, block-borders, concentric**, etc. given above, we shall concentrate our work in this direction on **prime magic squares**. This whole work is given in many parts.

3 Prime-Structured Magic Squares of Order 1220×1220

This work bring magic square of order 1220×1220 in prime numbers based on equal sum blocks of order 4. The blocks of order 4 are in such a way that all them are with distinct primes and of equal magic sums. Due to hight order, the work divided in 7 parts or 7 levels.

- Level 1: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 120×120 ;
- Level 2: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 160×160 ;
- Level 3: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 324×324 ;

- Level 4: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 484×484 ;
- Level 5: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 656×656 ;
- Level 6: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 896×896 ;
- Level 7: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 1220×1220 .

Let’s present each Level separately. In each Level, the magic square sums are the same for order 4. Going one level to another, the order of magic square increases, it also increased the magic sum of order 4. Moreover, all the primes are distinct for each Level.

3.1 Level 1: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 120×120

Lets see the following four examples:

4	mgc					4000012	4	mgc					4000012
		1153777	875209	1124797	846229	4000012			1367533	631753	1368253	632473	4000012
		905959	1934887	65119	1094047	4000012			629737	1979899	20107	1370269	4000012
		19249	1167637	832369	1980757	4000012			25933	1370623	629383	1974073	4000012
		1921027	22279	1977727	78979	4000012			1976809	17737	1982269	23197	4000012
		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012			4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012
4	mgc					4000012	4	mgc					4000012
		1413283	600469	1399537	586723	4000012			1302277	656809	1343197	697729	4000012
		624199	1942177	57829	1375807	4000012			751669	1592113	407893	1248337	4000012
		26317	1419247	580759	1973689	4000012			446569	1394893	605113	1553437	4000012
		1936213	38119	1961887	63793	4000012			1499497	356197	1643809	500509	4000012
		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012			4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012

These four examples are considered randomly from the magic square order 120×120 . It is composed of equal sums prime magic square of order 4×4 . All the entries are distinct primes. In this case the magic sums are:

$$S_{120 \times 120} := 120000360 \text{ and } S_{4 \times 4} := 4000012$$

This magic sum is based on the internal four entries of each block of order 4, It has some interesting properties. See below:

4	mgc					4000012					
	1413283	600469	1399537	586723	4000012	1413283	586723	1936213	63793	4000012	
	624199	1942177	57829	1375807	4000012	624199	26317	1375807	1973689	4000012	
	26317	1419247	580759	1973689	4000012	600469	1399537	38119	1961887	4000012	
	1936213	38119	1961887	63793	4000012	1942177	57829	1419247	580759	4000012	
	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012						

Looking above, the four members of each color are of same sum as of magic square. These properties are part of the **perfect magic square** of order 4. Since there are much more properties to be a **perfect magic square**, we shall call it as **semi-perfect prime magic squares**.

It gives us 29 blocks of magic squares of orders 8, 12, 16, ... ,120. All with equal sums distinct primes magic squares of order 4 with magic constant: $C=S/4:=1000003$.

This constant is so important that it helps us to know up to what order we can get **block-structured** prime magic square, i.e., this constant allow us to reach up to order 120×120 with equal sums blocks of order 4×4 having distinct primes. Below is an example of order 20 extracted from the order 120.

20	mgc																			20000060	
	1448989	621337	1378669	551017	1101253	889879	1110127	898753	1164967	918193	1081813	835039	1172467	922333	1077673	827539	1177843	866953	1133053	822163	20000060
	603817	1823149	176857	1396189	907723	1746127	253879	1092283	849019	1682413	317593	1150987	862669	1674913	325093	1137337	881233	1669537	330469	1118773	20000060
	129127	1454059	545947	1870879	281539	1137883	862123	1718467	308359	1169713	830293	1691647	291349	1173853	826153	1708657	272179	1178623	821383	1727827	20000060
	1818079	101467	1898539	181927	1709497	226123	1773883	290509	1677667	229693	1770313	322339	1673527	228913	1771093	326479	1668757	284899	1715107	331249	20000060
	1752397	251359	1748647	247609	1781173	258109	1741897	218833	1638913	329347	1670659	361093	1678639	354877	1645129	321367	1682389	355513	1644493	317617	20000060
	307423	1877353	122653	1692583	283303	1848577	151429	1716703	401053	1903339	96667	1598953	331777	1863613	136393	1668229	370537	1859863	140143	1629469	20000060
	80629	1770187	229819	1919377	90403	1784617	215389	1909603	94327	1676533	323473	1905679	126037	1678693	321313	1873969	89137	1684303	315703	1910869	20000060
	1859563	101113	1898893	140443	1845133	108709	1891297	154873	1865719	90793	1909213	134287	1863559	102829	1897177	136447	1857949	100333	1899673	142057	20000060
	1782289	235273	1764733	217717	1788433	209857	1790149	211573	1325557	661099	1338907	674449	1364617	666889	1333117	635389	1387417	652369	1347637	612589	20000060
	258127	1866973	133033	1741879	243829	1860829	139177	1756177	692239	1873507	126499	1307767	648259	1834447	165559	1351747	665719	1811647	188359	1334287	20000060
	93553	1783219	216787	1906453	108517	1790029	209977	1891489	122209	1339057	660949	1877797	155689	1367617	632389	1844317	136399	1388587	611419	1863607	20000060
	1866043	114547	1885459	133963	1859233	139297	1860709	140773	1860007	126349	1873657	139999	1831447	131059	1868947	168559	1810477	147409	1852597	189529	20000060
	1175569	836863	1163143	824437	1200349	861823	1138183	799657	1219843	857407	1142599	780163	1674997	288913	1711093	325009	1732267	260419	1739587	267739	20000060
	867487	1805653	194353	1132519	878833	1780873	219133	1121173	868957	1761379	238627	1131049	295129	1887433	112573	1704877	322549	1830163	169843	1677457	20000060
	163573	1187839	812167	1836433	150247	1210639	789367	1849759	176629	1246639	753367	1823377	181219	1713763	286243	1818787	126493	1743727	256279	1873513	20000060
	1793383	169657	1830349	206623	1770583	146677	1853329	229423	1734583	134587	1865419	265423	1848667	109903	1890103	151339	1818703	165703	1834303	181303	20000060
	1742989	299287	1700719	257017	1522483	474583	1525423	477523	1528237	461017	1538989	471769	1540879	493573	1506433	459127	1546759	457813	1542193	453247	20000060
	301867	1820509	179497	1698139	472057	1868983	131023	1527949	475669	1863229	136777	1524337	471217	1850587	149419	1528789	460063	1844707	155299	1539943	20000060
	152077	1760419	239587	1847929	137413	1523407	476599	1862593	140983	1536343	463663	1859023	137659	1541209	458797	1862347	149503	1547779	452227	1850503	20000060
	1803079	119797	1880209	196927	1868059	133039	1866967	131947	1855123	139423	1860583	144883	1850257	114643	1885363	149749	1843687	149713	1850293	156319	20000060
	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060

3.2 Level 2: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 160×160

Lets see the following four examples:

4	mgc				8000012	4	mgc				8000012
	2868527	133379	3866627	1131479	8000012		3273593	706049	3293957	726413	8000012
	562409	3400919	599087	3437597	8000012		985307	2331887	1668119	3014699	8000012
	867827	2568197	1431809	3132179	8000012		1327619	3191987	808019	2672387	8000012
	3701249	1897517	2102489	298757	8000012		2413493	1770089	2229917	1586513	8000012
	8000012	8000012	8000012	8000012	8000012		8000012	8000012	8000012	8000012	8000012
4	mgc				8000012	4	mgc				8000012
	2689007	1376423	2623583	1310999	8000012		2395763	269327	3730679	1604243	8000012
	1038629	3099419	900587	2961377	8000012		1871339	3678683	321323	2128667	8000012
	1087433	2603483	1396523	2912573	8000012		389057	2730593	1269413	3610949	8000012
	3184943	920687	3079319	815063	8000012		3343853	1321409	2678597	656153	8000012
	8000012	8000012	8000012	8000012	8000012		8000012	8000012	8000012	8000012	8000012

These four examples are considered randomly from the magic square order 160×160 . It is composed of equal sums prime magic square of order 4×4 . All the entries are distinct primes. In this case the magic sums are:

$$S_{160 \times 160} := 32000480 \text{ and } S_{4 \times 4} := 8000012$$

This magic sum is based on the internal four entries of each block of order 4, It has some interesting properties. See below:

4	mgc				8000012						
	3273593	706049	3293957	726413	8000012	3273593	726413	2413493	1586513	8000012	
	985307	2331887	1668119	3014699	8000012	985307	1327619	3014699	2672387	8000012	
	1327619	3191987	808019	2672387	8000012	706049	3293957	1770089	2229917	8000012	
	2413493	1770089	2229917	1586513	8000012	2331887	1668119	3191987	808019	8000012	
	8000012	8000012	8000012	8000012	8000012						

Looking above, the four members of each color are of same sum as of magic square. These properties are part of the **perfect magic square** of order 4. Since there are much more properties to be a **perfect magic square**, we shall call it as **semi-perfect prime magic squares**.

It gives us 39 blocks of magic squares of orders 8, 12, 16, ... ,160. All with equal sums distinct primes magic squares of order 4 with magic constant: $C=S/4:=2000003$.

This constant is so important that it helps us to know up to what order we can get **block-structured** prime magic square, i.e., this constant allow us to reach up to order 160×160 with equal sums blocks of order 4×4 having distinct primes. Below is an example of order 20 extracted from the order 160.

20	mgc																			40000060	
	3561023	348077	3651929	438983	3597563	388133	3611873	402443	3636233	408137	3591869	363773	3661529	369647	3630359	338477	2082527	1957517	2042489	1917479	40000060
	496949	3953009	46997	3503057	464753	3916469	83537	3535253	428003	3877799	122207	3572003	462713	3852503	147503	3537293	1872929	2732099	1267907	2127077	40000060
	19577	3591569	408437	3980429	47087	3623423	376583	3952919	78317	3656573	343433	3921689	96737	3734999	265007	3903269	1315229	2085299	1914707	2684777	40000060
	3922463	107357	3892649	77543	3890609	71987	3928019	109397	3857459	57503	3942503	142547	3779033	42863	3957143	220973	2729327	1225097	2774909	1270679	40000060
	2872967	1109609	2890397	1127039	2916107	945809	3054197	1083899	2947517	1009289	2990717	1052489	3052187	1019849	2980157	947819	2201357	1893599	2106407	1798649	40000060
	1151399	3946157	53849	2848607	1174049	3903017	96989	2825957	1044509	3871607	128399	2955497	1197929	3766937	233069	2802077	1904519	2755967	1244039	2095487	40000060
	42719	2886197	1113809	3957287	29009	2938277	1061729	3970997	140729	2951867	1048139	3859277	30839	3100067	899939	3969167	1149689	2212877	1787129	2850317	40000060
	3932927	58049	3941957	67079	3880847	212909	3787097	119159	3867257	167249	3832757	132749	3719057	113159	3886847	280949	2744447	1137569	2862437	1255559	40000060
	2090009	1780967	2219039	1909997	2229569	1798967	2201039	1770437	2270249	1844207	2155799	1729757	2363939	1679297	2320709	1636067	2144489	1868879	2131127	1855517	40000060
	1849037	3614609	385397	2150969	1847777	3475049	524957	2152229	1778747	3434369	565637	2221259	1832177	3340679	659327	2167829	1947107	2479667	1520339	2052899	40000060
	509867	2153519	1846487	3490139	457277	2239229	1760777	3542729	561797	2315399	1684607	3438209	495587	2396309	1603697	3504419	1480733	2196473	1803533	2519273	40000060
	3551099	450917	3549089	448907	3465389	486767	3513239	534617	3389219	406037	3593969	610787	3308309	583727	3416279	691697	2427683	1454993	2545013	1572323	40000060
	2172239	1590857	2409149	1827767	2343359	1634177	2365829	1656647	2368109	1822217	2177789	1631897	2381789	1653287	2346719	1618217	2262443	1748843	2251163	1737563	40000060
	1728767	3805979	194027	2271239	1741877	3634859	365147	2258129	1848107	3610109	389897	2151899	1853387	3596429	403577	2146619	1749383	3882737	117269	2250623	40000060
	432857	2312069	1687937	3567149	280337	2343779	1656227	3719669	183377	2377799	1622207	3816629	428567	2641949	1358057	3571439	159899	2316893	1683113	3840107	40000060
	3666149	291107	3708899	333857	3634439	387197	3612809	365567	3600419	189887	3810119	399587	3336269	108347	3891659	663737	3828287	51539	3948467	171719	40000060
	2405297	1798613	2201393	1594709	2100569	1732847	2267159	1899437	2134019	1867157	2132849	1865987	2311349	1773017	2226989	1688657	2639477	1748489	2251517	1360529	40000060
	1686389	3638213	361793	2313617	1745927	2630399	1369607	2254079	1772087	2596949	1403057	2227919	1725197	2419619	1580387	2274809	1581449	2877557	1122449	2418557	40000060
	302579	2437763	1562243	3697427	1684877	2262329	1737677	2315129	1678697	2315759	1684247	2321309	1586537	2354039	1645967	2413469	925409	2663357	1336649	3074597	40000060
	3605747	125423	3874583	394259	2468639	1374437	2625569	1531367	2415209	1220147	2779859	1584797	2376929	1453337	2546669	1623077	2853677	710609	3289397	1146329	40000060
40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060	40000060

3.3 Level 3: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 324×324

Lets see the following four examples:

4	mgc				40000076	4	mgc				40000076
	13217861	6152879	13847159	6782177	40000076		15333107	4594559	15405479	4666931	40000076
	5264267	15465647	4534391	14735771	40000076		182561	14976869	5023169	19817477	40000076
	6766469	13932029	6068009	13233569	40000076		4777001	10602569	9397469	15223037	40000076
	14751479	4449521	15550517	5248559	40000076		19707407	9826079	10173959	292631	40000076
	40000076	40000076	40000076	40000076	40000076		40000076	40000076	40000076	40000076	40000076
4	mgc				40000076	4	mgc				40000076
	11892527	8888939	11111099	8107511	40000076		16667627	8377877	11622161	3332411	40000076
	9893141	12837599	7162439	10106897	40000076		5673281	12550229	7449809	14326757	40000076
	7288301	13804019	6196019	12711737	40000076		7358291	18916979	1083059	12641747	40000076
	10926107	4469519	15530519	9073931	40000076		10300877	154991	19845047	9699161	40000076
	40000076	40000076	40000076	40000076	40000076		40000076	40000076	40000076	40000076	40000076

These four examples are considered randomly from the magic square order 324×324 . It is composed of equal sums prime magic square of order 4×4 . All the entries are distinct primes. In this case the magic sums are:

$$S_{324 \times 324} := 3240006156 \text{ and } S_{4 \times 4} := 40000076$$

This magic sum is based on the internal four entries of each block of order 4, It has some interesting properties. See below:

4	mgc				40000076						
	11892527	8888939	11111099	8107511	40000076		11892527	8107511	10926107	9073931	40000076
	9893141	12837599	7162439	10106897	40000076		9893141	7288301	10106897	12711737	40000076
	7288301	13804019	6196019	12711737	40000076		8888939	11111099	4469519	15530519	40000076
	10926107	4469519	15530519	9073931	40000076		12837599	7162439	13804019	6196019	40000076
	40000076	40000076	40000076	40000076	40000076						

Looking above, the four members of each color are of same sum as of magic square. These properties are part of the **perfect magic square** of order 4. Since there are much more properties to be a **perfect magic square**, we shall call it as **semi-perfect prime magic squares**.

It gives us 80 blocks of magic squares of orders 8, 12, 16, ... , 324. All with equal sums distinct primes magic squares of order 4 with magic constant $C=S/4:=10000019$.

This constant is so important that it helps us to know up to what order we can get **block-structured** prime magic square, i.e., this constant allow us to reach up to order 324×324 with equal sums blocks of order 4×4 having distinct primes. Below is an example of order 20 extracted from the order 324.

20	mgc																			200000380	
	19908197	4468199	15531839	91841	17748827	2264501	17735537	2251211	18368981	411617	19588421	1631057	13250177	3213887	16786151	6749861	18902717	1990481	18009557	1097321	200000380
	5039291	12033881	7966157	14960747	4329881	14650697	5349341	15670157	2920901	11906417	8093621	17079137	7629371	16281809	3718229	12370667	672869	12509741	7490297	19327169	200000380
	2031257	18920747	1079291	17968781	3496751	17974907	2025131	16503287	7955897	19521101	478937	12044141	3583241	13994699	6005339	16416797	8230799	19218767	781271	11769239	200000380
	13021331	4577249	15422789	6978707	14424617	5109971	14890067	5575421	10754297	8160941	11839097	9245741	15537287	6509681	13490357	4462751	12193691	6281087	13718951	7806347	200000380
	17859407	7794821	12205217	2140631	10829999	9374537	10625501	9170039	14039939	240257	19759781	5960099	16193831	2773019	17227019	3806207	15840371	9593861	10406177	4159667	200000380
	872411	11071799	8928239	19127627	9998279	16204469	3795569	10001759	505469	18785171	1214867	19494569	2433869	15977189	4022849	17566169	9894617	12229487	7770551	10105421	200000380
	4554611	12217559	7782479	15445427	5553269	13415939	6584099	14446769	7025567	14396009	5604029	12974471	1970237	12768881	7231157	18029801	10247	13815017	6185021	19989791	200000380
	16713647	8915897	11084141	3286391	13618529	1005131	18994907	6381509	18429101	6578639	13421399	1570937	19402139	8480987	11519051	597899	14254841	4361711	15638327	5745197	200000380
	13115717	3629597	16370441	6884321	10586099	8453381	11546657	9413939	16539857	4002281	15997757	3460181	12832037	1681259	18318779	7168001	10661897	4260131	15739907	9338141	200000380
	5809949	15202631	4797407	14190089	8244941	13619189	6380849	11755097	9778037	15164321	4835717	10222001	9733811	14739149	5260889	10266227	871571	18945317	1054721	19128467	200000380
	9957581	17201519	2798519	10042457	7699397	10735649	9264389	12300641	1879961	19901957	98081	18120077	4162421	14299379	5700659	15837617	8871101	10011707	9988331	11128937	200000380
	11116829	3966329	16033709	8883209	13469639	7191857	12808181	6530399	11802221	931517	19068521	8197817	13271807	9280289	10719749	6728231	19595507	6782921	13217117	404531	200000380
	14643329	1209281	18790757	5356709	10734359	7812461	12187577	9265679	13746311	94847	19905191	6253727	19837049	4757351	15242687	162989	18232469	7684421	12315617	1767569	200000380
	5338997	17423267	2576771	14661041	8714609	12058679	7941359	11285429	8982929	15219389	4780649	11017109	1664417	10466279	9533759	18335621	2955539	10402607	9597431	17044499	200000380
	5278271	17327117	2672921	14721767	8048627	10290557	9709481	11951411	5019767	16714631	3285407	14980271	7531721	19336439	663599	12468317	2328401	12151409	7848629	17671637	200000380
	14739479	4040411	15959627	5260559	12502481	9838379	10161659	7497557	12251069	7971209	12028829	7748969	10966889	5440007	14560031	9033149	16483667	9761639	10238399	3516371	200000380
	11110097	7692437	12307601	8889941	19212491	4413917	15586121	787547	10750829	6396857	13603181	9249209	13061039	9630521	10369517	6938999	13833791	4280249	15719789	6166247	200000380
	7178657	16937861	3062177	12821381	4969091	11173637	8826401	15030947	45281	19739189	260849	19954757	1908047	16533227	3466811	18091991	3404309	17806589	2193449	16595729	200000380
	4175981	10512617	9487421	15824057	923147	15490781	4509257	19076891	9485087	10771139	9228899	10514951	8784731	13348007	6652031	11215307	7565687	16444091	3555947	12434351	200000380
	17535341	4857161	15142877	2464697	14895347	8921741	11078297	5104691	19718879	3092891	16907147	281159	16246259	488321	19511717	3753779	15196289	1469147	18530891	4803749	200000380
	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380	200000380

3.4 Level 4: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 484×484

Lets see the following four examples:

4	mgc				100000036	4	mgc				100000036
	35288017	6072427	43927591	14712001	100000036		31314667	23476501	26523517	18685351	100000036
	6155311	49345201	654817	43844707	100000036		19606351	44605081	5394937	30393667	100000036
	14713471	40789981	9210037	35286547	100000036		421987	27262717	22737301	49578031	100000036
	43843237	3792427	46207591	6156781	100000036		48657031	4655737	45344281	1342987	100000036
	100000036	100000036	100000036	100000036	100000036		100000036	100000036	100000036	100000036	100000036
4	mgc				100000036	4	mgc				100000036
	27296371	13803961	36196057	22703647	100000036		27027811	10610779	39389239	22972207	100000036
	22673527	40585117	9414901	27326491	100000036		16088089	45926449	4073569	33911929	100000036
	21409321	39260671	10739347	28590697	100000036		19990777	36060901	13939117	30009241	100000036
	28620817	6350287	43649731	21379201	100000036		36893359	7401907	42598111	13106659	100000036
	100000036	100000036	100000036	100000036	100000036		100000036	100000036	100000036	100000036	100000036

These four examples are considered randomly from the magic square order 484×484 . It is composed of equal sums prime magic square of order 4×4 . All the entries are distinct primes. In this case the magic sums are:

$$S_{484 \times 484} := 12100004356 \text{ and } S_{4 \times 4} := 100000036$$

This magic sum is based on the internal four entries of each block of order 4, It has some interesting properties. See below:

4	mgc				100000036						
	35288017	6072427	43927591	14712001	100000036		35288017	14712001	43843237	6156781	100000036
	6155311	49345201	654817	43844707	100000036		6155311	14713471	43844707	35286547	100000036
	14713471	40789981	9210037	35286547	100000036		6072427	43927591	3792427	46207591	100000036
	43843237	3792427	46207591	6156781	100000036		49345201	654817	40789981	9210037	100000036
	100000036	100000036	100000036	100000036	100000036						

Looking above, the four members of each color are of same sum as of magic square. These properties are part of the **perfect magic square** of order 4. Since there are much more properties to be a **perfect magic square**, we shall call it as **semi-perfect prime magic squares**.

It gives us 120 blocks of magic squares of orders 8, 12, 16, ... , 484. All with equal sums distinct primes magic squares of order 4 with magic constant $C=S/4:=25000009$.

This constant is so important that it helps us to know up to what order we can get **block-structured** prime magic square, i.e., this constant allow us to reach up to order 484×484 with equal sums blocks of order 4×4 having distinct primes. Below is an example of order 20 extracted from the order 484.

20	mgc																			500000180	
	36463039	23787877	26212141	13536979	31836307	23552941	26447077	18163711	44351689	22385089	27614929	5648329	43672687	2683621	47316397	6327331	27513391	24527761	25472257	22486627	500000180
	661777	42573931	7426087	49338241	12414469	26691001	23309017	37585549	4170541	29034769	20965249	45829477	6126457	48411241	1588777	43873561	21954799	26006437	23993581	28045219	500000180
	15736939	31898689	18101329	34263079	22291639	25069687	24930331	27708379	5599219	27507871	22492147	44400799	6819781	48702817	1297201	43180237	22397227	25385209	24614809	27602791	500000180
	47138281	1739539	48260479	2861737	33457621	24686407	25313611	16542397	45878587	21072307	28927711	4121431	43381111	202357	49797661	6618907	28134619	24080629	25919389	21865399	500000180
	25957081	14673577	35326441	24042937	47576329	20617237	29382781	2423689	46984297	1541347	48458671	3015721	49293967	4376347	45623671	706051	47289577	21425587	28574431	2710441	500000180
	17734027	49459117	540901	32265991	3382129	31762219	18237799	46617889	3797671	40460881	9539137	46202347	10676329	25304911	24695107	39323689	23702269	28057441	21942577	26297749	500000180
	15408361	34515631	15484387	34591657	13858051	44155021	5844997	36141967	1744009	39971119	10028899	48256009	12742099	47311237	2688781	37257919	3252349	49591177	408841	46747669	500000180
	40900567	1351711	48648307	9099451	35183527	3465559	46534459	14816491	47474059	18026689	31973329	2525959	27287641	23007541	26992477	22712377	25755841	925831	49074187	24244177	500000180
	40252897	234811	49765207	9747121	33418969	10147141	39852877	16581049	44480011	5082331	44917687	5520007	42114607	11944321	38055697	7885411	47919169	17218039	32781979	2080849	500000180
	22631431	34671157	15328861	27368587	9432481	48727027	1272991	40567537	5068597	40459717	9540301	44931421	5474611	46775941	3224077	44525407	6586399	25140301	24859717	43413619	500000180
	11690881	49499227	500791	38309137	13370809	38368219	11631799	36629209	1939891	36428191	13571827	48060127	3435007	39914737	10085281	46565011	7907467	35472469	14527549	42092551	500000180
	25424827	15594841	34405177	24575191	43777777	2757649	47242369	6222241	48511537	18029797	31970221	1488481	48975811	1365037	48634981	1024207	37587001	22169227	27830791	12413017	500000180
	26775877	13069741	36930277	23224141	31380511	7437217	42562801	18619507	28011169	21086671	28913347	21988849	29499487	12755851	37244167	20500531	49129651	7477117	42522901	870367	500000180
	18375631	33831157	16168861	31624387	21915547	40716889	9283129	28084471	1562269	47643667	2356351	48437749	22249231	42490807	7509211	27750787	986437	28249747	21750271	49013581	500000180
	23614291	29372797	20627221	26385727	21396799	46790221	3209797	28603219	23357419	28585657	21414361	26642599	19372471	43111447	6888571	30627547	22304761	49800211	199807	27695257	500000180
	31234237	23726341	26273677	18765781	25307179	5055709	44944309	24692839	47069179	2684041	47315977	2930839	28878847	1641931	48358087	21121171	27579187	14472961	35527057	22420831	500000180
	48285169	20338207	29661811	1714849	45941809	1148167	48851851	4058209	42182947	6715771	43284247	7817071	47254621	2144437	47855581	2745397	27795379	15646381	34353637	22204639	500000180
	14306671	26455591	23544427	35693347	2728939	29340151	20659867	47271079	6399577	46869061	3130957	43600441	2707657	47494561	2505457	47292361	11444929	42385927	7614091	38555089	500000180
	11932567	49265131	734887	38067451	21864019	45816691	4183327	28135999	4735441	42369937	7630081	45264577	2506447	47217871	2782147	47493571	16192861	25614439	24385579	33807157	500000180
	25475629	3941107	46058911	24524389	29465269	23695027	26304991	20534749	46682071	4045267	45954751	3317947	47531311	3143167	46856851	2468707	44566867	16353289	33646729	5433151	500000180
	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180	500000180

3.5 Level 5: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 656×656

Lets see the following four examples:

4	mgc				200000068	4	mgc				200000068
	73214731	23805163	76194871	26785303	200000068		84686551	31908313	68091721	15313483	200000068
	10377793	85479103	14520931	89622241	200000068		44425327	53318227	46681807	55574707	200000068
	38516221	80802511	19197523	61483813	200000068		8138983	75255571	24744463	91861051	200000068
	77891323	9913291	90086743	22108711	200000068		62749207	39517957	60482077	37250827	200000068
	200000068	200000068	200000068	200000068	200000068		200000068	200000068	200000068	200000068	200000068
4	mgc				200000068	4	mgc				200000068
	85053061	18488521	81511513	14946973	200000068		85387087	45866287	54133747	14612947	200000068
	41309953	64908793	35091241	58690081	200000068		5903761	74378323	25621711	94096273	200000068
	20075593	96400393	3599641	79924441	200000068		16980907	68037097	31962937	83019127	200000068
	53561461	20202361	79797673	46438573	200000068		91728313	11718361	88281673	8271721	200000068
	200000068	200000068	200000068	200000068	200000068		200000068	200000068	200000068	200000068	200000068

These four examples are considered randomly from the magic square order 656×656 . It is composed of equal sums prime magic square of order 4×4 . All the entries are distinct primes. In this case the magic sums are:

$$S_{656 \times 656} := 32800011152 \text{ and } S_{4 \times 4} := 200000068$$

This magic sum is based on the internal four entries of each block of order 4, It has some interesting properties. See below:

4	mgc				200000068						
	85053061	18488521	81511513	14946973	200000068		85053061	14946973	53561461	46438573	200000068
	41309953	64908793	35091241	58690081	200000068		41309953	20075593	58690081	79924441	200000068
	20075593	96400393	3599641	79924441	200000068		18488521	81511513	20202361	79797673	200000068
	53561461	20202361	79797673	46438573	200000068		64908793	35091241	96400393	3599641	200000068
	200000068	200000068	200000068	200000068	200000068						

Looking above, the four members of each color are of same sum as of magic square. These properties are part of the **perfect magic square** of order 4. Since there are much more properties to be a **perfect magic square**, we shall call it as **semi-perfect prime magic squares**.

It gives us 163 blocks of magic squares of orders 8, 12, 16, ... , 656. All with equal sums distinct primes magic squares of order 4 with magic constant $C=S/4:=50000017$.

This constant is so important that it helps us to know up to what order we can get **block-structured** prime magic square, i.e., this constant allow us to reach up to order 656×656 with equal sums blocks of order 4×4 having distinct primes. Below is an example of order 20 extracted from the order 656.

20	mgc																			100000340	
	56711311	8564071	91435963	43288723	65910007	1446001	98554033	34090027	51625723	43094797	56905237	48374311	51484291	48036061	51963973	48515743	83086903	43210267	56789767	16913131	100000340
	18805243	94603897	5396137	81194791	36738421	95277313	4722721	63261613	36252841	94614991	5385043	63747193	25425007	98260243	1739791	74575027	20452057	70790761	29209273	79547977	100000340
	29143273	55974967	44025067	70856761	6990463	70826143	29173891	93009571	17733757	51852967	48147067	82266277	23346493	50000257	49999777	76653541	5257591	62674147	37325887	94742443	100000340
	95340241	40857133	59142901	4659793	90361177	32450611	67549423	9638857	94387747	10437313	89562721	5612287	99744277	3703507	96296527	255757	91203517	23324893	76675141	8796517	100000340
	85598113	7483681	92516353	14401921	66542143	17873203	82126831	33457891	90864913	26304241	73695793	9135121	70830811	37202461	62797573	29169223	77891641	19490467	80509567	22108393	100000340
	29551141	63566617	36433417	70448893	37293661	80422471	19577563	62706373	18012091	60042013	39958021	81987943	11042233	71488867	28511167	88957801	16264177	76792657	23207377	83735857	100000340
	15795427	80109343	19890691	84204607	44014303	94814653	5185381	55985731	8797501	68581363	31418671	91202533	32651923	56844577	43155457	67348111	8045533	56885581	43114453	91954501	100000340
	69055387	48840427	51159607	30944647	52149961	6889741	93110293	47850073	82325563	45072451	54927583	17674471	85475101	34464163	65535871	14524933	97798717	46831363	53168671	2201317	100000340
	91215031	21900421	78099613	8785003	79983151	48974953	51025081	20016883	54494053	34238251	65761783	45505981	84045817	15864691	84135343	15954217	85053061	18488521	81511513	14946973	100000340
	39028777	52786303	47213731	60971257	31756003	59466481	40533553	68244031	46078531	95357377	4642657	53921503	17260081	95150023	4850011	82739953	41309953	64908793	35091241	58690081	100000340
	5633623	79878697	20121337	94366411	35190613	86379331	13620703	64809421	924601	51348547	48651487	99075433	2827687	83329357	16670677	97172347	20075593	96400393	3599641	79924441	100000340
	64122637	45434647	54565387	35877397	53070301	5179303	94820731	46929733	98502883	19055893	80944141	1497151	95866483	5655997	94344037	4133551	53561461	20202361	79797673	46438573	100000340
	60651421	9777973	90222061	39348613	80382637	49394173	50605861	19617397	52014757	40929307	59070727	47985277	54955123	12740671	87259363	45044911	78278293	48404353	51595681	21721741	100000340
	27789043	90416773	9583261	72210991	2452141	52258147	47741887	97547893	48257281	82554187	17445847	51742753	42322237	99158971	841063	57677797	15815161	57948991	42051043	84184873	100000340
	44934061	84442651	15557383	55065973	46889113	62364607	37635427	53110921	32842417	67683331	32316703	67157617	25011247	76402633	23597401	74988787	49705561	80026231	19973803	50294473	100000340
	66625543	15362671	84637363	33374491	70276177	35983141	64016893	29723857	66885613	8833243	91166791	33114421	77711461	11697793	88302241	22288573	56201053	13620493	86379541	43798981	100000340
	80985901	47164591	52835443	19014133	89394427	48367993	51632041	10605607	83085193	42828547	57171487	16914841	92115811	48052057	51947977	7884223	50093647	48124123	51875911	49906387	100000340
	26676613	59427343	40572691	73323421	14653393	56008321	43991713	85346641	7802323	65768821	34231213	92197711	21277153	50847157	49152877	78722881	32207083	98665291	1334743	67792951	100000340
	5369137	53444827	46555207	94630897	11654191	61104691	38895343	88345843	14396911	54138373	45861661	85603123	1735033	58090897	41909137	98265001	20502991	51562591	48437443	79497043	100000340
	86968417	39963307	60036727	13031617	84298057	34519063	65480971	15701977	94715641	37264327	62735707	5284393	84872071	43009957	56990077	15127963	97196347	1648063	98351971	2803687	100000340
	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340	100000340

3.6 Level 6: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 896×896

Lets see the following four examples:

4	mgc				400000028	4	mgc				400000028
	184641761	24558071	175441943	15358253	400000028		199998107	84981731	115018283	1907	400000028
	5969993	137575367	62424647	194030021	400000028		22032557	118579733	81420281	177967457	400000028
	59984543	172813397	27186617	140015471	400000028		20655941	161264417	38735597	179344073	400000028
	149403731	65053193	134946821	50596283	400000028		157313423	35174147	164825867	42686591	400000028
	400000028	400000028	400000028	400000028	400000028		400000028	400000028	400000028	400000028	400000028
4	mgc				400000028	4	mgc				400000028
	111976961	95894021	104105993	88023053	400000028		169640327	42325397	157674617	30359687	400000028
	62657993	159820223	40179791	137342021	400000028		63618701	153303317	46696697	136381313	400000028
	82440863	128872973	71127041	117559151	400000028		3301637	159504281	40495733	196698377	400000028
	142924211	15412811	184587203	57075803	400000028		163439363	44867033	155132981	36560651	400000028
	400000028	400000028	400000028	400000028	400000028		400000028	400000028	400000028	400000028	400000028

These four examples are considered randomly from the magic square order 896×896 . It is composed of equal sums prime magic square of order 4×4 . All the entries are distinct primes. In this case the magic sums are:

$$S_{896 \times 896} := 89600006272 \text{ and } S_{4 \times 4} := 400000028$$

This magic sum is based on the internal four entries of each block of order 4, It has some interesting properties. See below:

4	mgc				400000028						
	111976961	95894021	104105993	88023053	400000028		111976961	142924211	88023053	57075803	400000028
	62657993	159820223	40179791	137342021	400000028		62657993	82440863	137342021	117559151	400000028
	82440863	128872973	71127041	117559151	400000028		95894021	104105993	15412811	184587203	400000028
	142924211	15412811	184587203	57075803	400000028		159820223	40179791	128872973	71127041	400000028
	400000028	400000028	400000028	400000028	400000028						

Looking above, the four members of each color are of same sum as of magic square. These properties are part of the **perfect magic square** of order 4. Since there are much more properties to be a **perfect magic square**, we shall call it as **semi-perfect prime magic squares**.

It gives us 223 blocks of magic squares of orders 8, 12, 16, ... , 896. All with equal sums distinct primes magic squares of order 4 with magic constant $C=S/4:=100000007$.

This constant is so important that it helps us to know up to what order we can get **block-structured** prime magic square, i.e., this constant allow us to reach up to order 896×896 with equal sums blocks of order 4×4 having distinct primes. Below is an example of order 20 extracted from the order 896.

20	mgc																			2000000140	
	179516021	84308351	115691663	20483993	174113603	80446733	119553281	25886411	186743957	74104637	125895377	13256057	121721153	95132243	104867771	78278861	102037571	8671367	191328647	97962443	2000000140
	83269601	135948053	64051961	116730413	5295701	141652421	58347593	194704313	39955541	108021773	91978241	160044473	70998371	135069251	64930763	129001643	71804417	191846597	8153417	128195597	2000000140
	1277723	179527391	20472623	198722291	55618727	150794027	49205987	144381287	20244167	141709367	58290647	179755847	97186613	146696513	53303501	102813401	32500613	100226741	99773273	167499401	2000000140
	135936683	216233	199783781	64063331	164971997	27106847	172893167	35028017	153056363	76164251	123835763	46943651	110093891	23102021	176897993	89906123	193657427	99255323	100744691	6342587	2000000140
	189168953	69827837	130172177	10831061	120267071	4070447	195929567	79732943	183859451	33759053	166240961	16140563	134159147	82966073	117033941	65840867	197941301	17857451	182142563	2058713	2000000140
	20023391	129144161	70855853	179976623	29852177	193591553	6408461	170147837	70147127	105477527	94522487	129852887	57624173	170814197	29185817	142375841	79749053	105799997	94200017	120250961	2000000140
	71223917	198729347	1270667	128776097	53545313	117523157	82476857	146454701	37074533	180418061	19581953	162925481	46216451	142973087	57026927	153783563	15463793	196895417	3104597	184536221	2000000140
	119583767	2298683	197701331	80416247	196335467	84814871	115185143	3664547	108918917	80345387	119654627	91081097	162000257	3246671	196753343	37999757	106845881	79447163	120552851	93154133	2000000140
	110410103	59415677	140584337	89589911	179437961	39391337	160608677	20562053	151668557	68173811	131826203	48331457	135062777	20773091	179226923	64937237	119177417	29525777	170474237	80822597	2000000140
	70468571	195805661	4194353	129531443	83471033	107742647	92257367	116528981	6631271	149327393	50672621	193368743	24111887	193828097	6171917	175888127	70799207	184229417	15770597	129200807	2000000140
	55796837	142891247	57108767	144203177	11215307	161304881	38695133	188784707	59829317	119125067	80874947	140170697	97196933	185262443	14737571	102803081	17665061	111048491	88951523	182334953	2000000140
	163324517	1887443	198112571	36675497	125875727	91561163	108438851	74124287	181870883	63373757	136626257	18129131	143628431	136397	199863617	56371583	192358343	75196343	124803671	7641671	2000000140
	196882223	67969523	132030491	3117791	165386531	53492321	146507693	34613483	111921143	21320297	178679717	88078871	155777603	35122487	164877527	44222411	133485827	62097911	137902103	66514187	2000000140
	166631	145480421	54519593	199833383	9776693	134296157	65703857	190223321	9755777	177786611	22213403	190244237	28388111	140353517	59646497	171611903	25071353	145956743	54043271	174928661	2000000140
	3014777	142426247	57573767	196985237	71398763	146244647	53755367	128601251	98502161	109886807	90113207	101497853	52912091	133208897	66791117	147087923	98500151	136499873	63500141	101499863	2000000140
	199936397	44123837	155876177	63617	153438041	65966903	134033111	46561973	179820947	91006313	108993701	20179067	162922223	91315127	108684887	37077791	142942697	55445501	144554513	57057317	2000000140
	105772787	28321103	171678911	94227227	105363371	88224281	111775733	94636643	150393311	86971853	113028161	49606703	114279461	56204627	143795387	85720553	192308843	66407927	133592087	7691171	2000000140
	96633071	182565731	17434283	103366943	89491991	194558003	5442011	110508023	15335987	141829607	58170407	184664027	70891187	185447303	14552711	129108827	34257581	117046991	82953023	165742433	2000000140
	85357553	176101901	23898113	114642461	6143063	100919771	99080243	193856951	55435943	113388131	86611883	144564071	25682207	110579591	89420423	174317807	2110877	138033107	61966907	197889137	2000000140
	112236617	13011293	186988721	87763397	199001603	16297973	183702041	998411	178834787	57810437	142189577	21165227	189147173	47768507	152231507	10852841	171322727	78512003	121488011	28677287	2000000140
	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140	2000000140

3.7 Level 7: Block-Structured Prime Magic Square of Order 1220×1220

Lets see the following four examples:

4	mgc				799999964	4	mgc				799999964
	217453823	98153369	301846613	182546159	799999964		336064793	137401109	262598873	63935189	799999964
	103964849	354381659	45618323	296035133	799999964		62535731	260514269	139485713	337464251	799999964
	113461013	206715203	193284779	286538969	799999964		178032251	373211873	26788109	221967731	799999964
	365120279	140749733	259250249	34879703	799999964		223367189	28872713	371127269	176632793	799999964
	799999964	799999964	799999964	799999964	799999964		799999964	799999964	799999964	799999964	799999964
4	mgc				799999964	4	mgc				799999964
	257964191	142277141	257722841	142035791	799999964		241066283	1659101	398340881	158933699	799999964
	66133121	363926051	36073931	333866861	799999964		185379749	370274579	29725403	214620233	799999964
	105340181	251327771	148672211	294659801	799999964		157161443	394948373	5051609	242838539	799999964
	370562471	42469001	357530981	29437511	799999964		216392489	33117911	366882071	183607493	799999964
	799999964	799999964	799999964	799999964	799999964		799999964	799999964	799999964	799999964	799999964

These four examples are considered randomly from the magic square order 1220×1220 . It is composed of equal sums prime magic square of order 4×4 . All the entries are distinct primes. In this case the magic sums are:

$$S_{1220 \times 1220} := 243999989020 \text{ and } S_{4 \times 4} := 799999964$$

This magic sum is based on the internal four entries of each block of order 4, It has some interesting properties. See below:

4	mgc				799999964						
	336064793	137401109	262598873	63935189	799999964		336064793	223367189	63935189	176632793	799999964
	62535731	260514269	139485713	337464251	799999964		62535731	178032251	337464251	221967731	799999964
	178032251	373211873	26788109	221967731	799999964		137401109	262598873	28872713	371127269	799999964
	223367189	28872713	371127269	176632793	799999964		260514269	139485713	373211873	26788109	799999964
	799999964	799999964	799999964	799999964	799999964						

Looking above, the four members of each color are of same sum as of magic square. These properties are part of the **perfect magic square** of order 4. Since there are much more properties to be a **perfect magic square**, we shall call it as **semi-perfect prime magic squares**.

It gives us 304 blocks of magic squares of orders 8, 12, 16, ... , 1220. All with equal sums distinct primes magic squares of order 4 with magic constant $C=S/4:=199999991$.

This constant is so important that it helps us to know up to what order we can get **block-structured** prime magic square, i.e., this constant allow us to reach up to order 1220×1220 with equal sums blocks of order 4×4 having distinct primes. Below is an example of order 20 extracted from the order 1220.

Remark 1. The *excel files* of complete work are also attached.

20	mgc																			3999999820	
364229003	18084779	381915203	35770979	209486033	181815203	218184779	190513949	213592991	24736259	375263723	186406991	253246373	38689493	361310489	146753609	380800649	10973033	389026949	19199333	3999999820	
114781889	235787243	164212739	285218093	148894541	383105609	16894373	251105441	176758031	338483333	61516649	223241951	171851591	258027839	141972143	228148391	6538853	395452469	4547513	393461129	3999999820	
87253259	366280433	33719549	312746723	67027619	217999871	182000111	332972363	187216871	329644253	70355729	212783111	169602539	305974751	94025231	230397443	15039803	378632459	21367523	384960179	3999999820	
233735813	179847509	220152473	166264169	374591771	17079281	382920701	25408211	222432071	107136119	292863863	177567911	205299461	197307881	202692101	194700521	397620659	14942003	385057979	2379323	3999999820	
397075589	53150051	346849931	2924393	371511563	194591393	205408589	28488419	218918309	126430079	273569903	181081673	247906793	42843173	357156809	152093189	386703929	10445819	389554163	13296053	3999999820	
2968871	302962523	97037459	397031111	49032623	262772819	137227163	350967359	96891989	398825213	1174769	303107993	102992639	383614139	16385843	297007343	190901831	212527703	187472279	209098151	3999999820	
78629951	378712559	21287423	321370031	7403819	262232423	137767559	392596163	90905363	224459219	175540763	309094619	145230083	327650483	72349499	254769899	18476993	395314421	4685561	381522989	3999999820	
321325553	65174831	334825151	78674429	372051959	80403329	319596653	27948023	393284303	50285453	349714529	6715679	303870449	45892169	354107813	96129533	203917211	181712021	218287961	196082771	3999999820	
347904749	163237691	236762291	52095233	296167349	154561973	245438009	103832633	232468661	182657093	217342889	167531321	307707251	192937523	207062459	92292731	286763909	52792391	347207591	113236073	3999999820	
191496581	203070443	196929539	208503401	91810913	217458341	182541641	308189069	197467181	358537919	41462063	202532801	17779859	264933059	135066923	382220123	130068563	312405551	87594431	269931419	3999999820	
15623303	305999861	94000121	384376679	198861071	300465059	99534923	201138911	3759881	224702339	175297643	396240101	192734543	290861999	109137983	207265439	171858473	387860441	12139541	228141509	3999999820	
244975331	127691969	272308013	155024651	213160631	127514591	272485391	186839351	366304241	34102613	365897369	33695741	281778311	51267383	348732599	118221671	211309019	46941581	353058401	188690963	3999999820	
250681733	22335353	377664629	149318249	300484103	95969873	304030109	99515879	325676963	132698333	267301649	74323019	284205209	62408639	337591343	115794773	242655701	16847189	383152793	157344281	3999999820	
103897139	392468639	7531343	296102843	93124373	230622659	169377323	306875609	72677711	361800059	38199923	327322271	93663953	354590213	45409769	306336029	146007791	311261663	88738319	253992191	3999999820	
74454701	272183981	127816001	325545281	155871899	280587173	119412809	244128083	19556651	305388383	94611599	380443331	71416913	288081533	111918449	328583069	154388579	296969471	103030511	245611403	3999999820	
370966391	113011991	286987991	29033591	250519589	192820259	207179723	149480393	382088639	113189	399886793	17911343	350713889	94919579	305080403	49286093	256947893	174921641	225078341	143052089	3999999820	
302879813	193919669	206080313	97120169	338160203	141286829	258713153	61839779	387009671	36436079	363563903	12990311	341640293	37437779	362562203	58359689	369508673	131402903	268597079	30491309	3999999820	
199068659	210208703	189791279	200931323	58597001	253407929	146592053	341402981	4087631	327413711	72586271	395912351	4223519	272704829	127295153	395776463	29574029	246814409	153185573	370425953	3999999820	
6868109	221905133	178094849	393131873	191124911	379450283	20549699	208875071	23987231	329507951	70492031	376012751	136600733	296809703	103190279	263399249	7854773	223260593	176739389	392145209	3999999820	
291183383	173966459	226033523	108816599	212117849	25854923	374145059	187882133	384915431	106642223	293357759	15084551	317535419	193047653	206952329	82464563	393062489	198522059	201477923	6937493	3999999820	
3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820	3999999820

4 Author’s Contribution to Recreation of Numbers and Magic Squares

- (i) **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers - <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>.
- (ii) **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares - <https://numbers-magic.com/?cat=3>. Also for the publications on magic squares see the link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>.

References

- [1] **H.E. Dudeney**, Amusements in Mathematics, The Authors' Club, 1917.
- [2] **H. Harvey**, Prime Numbers Magic Squares <http://recmath.org/MagicSquares/primesqr.htm>
- [3] **C. Riveira**, The Prime Puzzles and Problem Connections, <https://www.primepuzzles.net/>
- [4] **H. White**, Bordered Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/BorderedMagicSquares.html>
- [5] **H. White**, Magic Squares of Prime Numbers, <https://budshaw.ca/PrimeMagicSquares.html>
- [6] **Makarova, Natalia**, Concentric magic squares of primes,
<http://primesmagicgames.altervista.org/wp/forums/topic/concentric-magic-squares-of-primes/>.
Also refers: <http://www.natalimak1.narod.ru/sqmin1.htm>; <http://www.natalimak1.narod.ru/sqmin2.htm>;
<http://www.natalimak1.narod.ru/sqmin3.htm>; <http://www.klassikpoez.narod.ru/glavnaja.htm>.
- **Prime Magic Squares**
- [7] **Inder J. Taneja**, Single-Layer Bordered Even and Odd Orders Primes Magic Squares: Orders 120 and 121, **Zenodo**, May June 16, 2026, pp. 1-36, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20723312>. Web-site links: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19224> and <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19258>.
- [8] **Inder J. Taneja**, Higher Order Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Order 1220 Multiples of 4, **Zenodo**, , June 17, 2026, pp. 1-27, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20723328>. Web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19291>.
- [9] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 6 to 14, **Zenodo**, June 16, 2026, pp. 1-39, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20723272> Web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19319>.
- [10] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 15 to 23, **Zenodo**, June 16, 2026, pp. 1-69, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20723291>. Web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19410>.
- [11] **Inder J. Taneja**, Higher Order Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 99 and 105 Multiples of 3, 5 and 7, In Preparation.

- [12] **Inder J. Taneja**, Higher Order Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 108, 121 and 117 Multiples 9, 11 and 13, In Preparation.
- [13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Higher Order Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 114, 96 and 100 Multiples of 6, 8 and 10, In Preparation.
- [14] **Inder J. Taneja**, Higher Order Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 120 and 140 Multiples of 12 and 14, In Preparation.
- [15] **Inder J. Taneja**, Higher Order Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Order 128 Multiples 4 and 16, In Preparation.
- [16] **Inder J. Taneja**, Higher Order Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Multiples of Orders 15, 17 and 19, In Preparation.
- [17] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 24 to 31, In Preparation.
- [18] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 32 to 38, In Preparation.
- [19] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 39 to 45, In Preparation.
- [20] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 46 to 51, In Preparation.

• Block-Wise Magic Squares

- [21] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 8 to 108, May 15, 2019, pp. 1-43, **Zenodo**, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2843326>.
- [22] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order $4k$, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-17, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554288>.
- [23] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>.
- [24] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders $3k$ and $6k$, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554895>.

- [25] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Unequal Sums Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-52, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555260>.
- [26] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 12 to 36, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-53, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555343>.
- [27] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 39 to 45, **Zenodo**, February 2, 2019, pp. 1-73, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555889>.
- [28] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 10 to 47. **Zenodo**, January 14, 2021, pp. 1-185, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437783>.
- [29] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Odd Order Multiples, **Zenodo**, February 10, 2021, pp. 1-75, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527739>
- [30] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Even Order Multiples, **Zenodo**, February 10, 2021, pp. 1-96, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527746>

• **Block-Bordered Magic Squares**

- [31] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - I, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-81, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990291>.
- [32] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - II, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-90, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990293>.
- [33] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - III, **Zenodo**, September 01, 2020, pp. 1-93, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4011213>.

• **Double-Digit Bordered Magic Squares**

- [34] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 4: Orders 8 to 24, **Zenodo**, April, 26, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866956>.

- [35] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 28 and 32, **Zenodo**, April, 26, 2023, pp. 1-36, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866981>.
- [36] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 10, 14, 18 and 22, **Zenodo**, April, 30, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880931>.
- [37] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 26 and 30, **Zenodo**, April, 30, 2023, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880937>.
- [38] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 36 and 40, **Zenodo**, May, 04, 2023, pp. 1-41, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7896709>.
- [39] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 34 and 38, **Zenodo**, May 10, 2023, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7922571>.
- [40] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Double Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 7 to 108, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8230214>.

• Cornered Magic Squares

- [41] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Order 6, **Zenodo**, May 23, 2023, pp. 1-23, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7960679>.
- [42] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 13, **Zenodo**, June 03, 2023, pp. 1-71, <https://10.5281/zenodo.8000467>.
- [43] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 14 to 24, **Zenodo**, June 03, 2023, pp. 1-39, <https://10.5281/zenodo.8000471>.
- [44] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 81, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-27, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8231157>.
- [45] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares in Construction of Magic Squares of Orders 16, 20, 24 and 28, **Zenodo**, August 23, 2023, <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=10172>.

- [46] **Inder J. Taneja**, Striped and Semi-Striped Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 6 to 50, <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=15048>, March 17, 2025
- [47] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 108, **Zenodo**, January 29, 2025, pp. 1-33, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14759238>.
-